

D1.1: Initial specification information product catalogue fulfilling societal/policy needs

Work Package	1
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1. Summary

Work Package (WP) 1 of OBAMA-NEXT is devoted to “Engagement of stakeholders and identification of product needs”. Hence, **the objectives of WP1 are:** (i) Engage stakeholders with complementary roles in marine policies through an approach that enables a dynamic interface (Task T1.1), (ii) for identifying and co-working on data needs (T1.2); (iii) towards meeting the expectations of the implementing authorities and being fit for endorsement by policymakers (T1.3); and (iv) transferring generated knowledge and lessons learnt (T1.4).

One of the WP1 outcomes is the definition of a catalogue of information products that meets the requirements of stakeholders and policy makers. The development of this catalogue began with an exploratory phase to identify the issues of relevance for stakeholder needs and to agree on the scope and specification of the information products. **Deliverable 1.1 describes the state of the art of the first stage of the process regarding the definition of the catalogue of OBAMA-NEXT information products.**

The following activities were carried out:

- (i) an online survey with members of the Practitioners Advisory Board (PAB) to identify their priorities and needs in terms of marine biodiversity information products;
- (ii) an online survey with selected stakeholders of relevance in the project’s Learning Sites (identified by project partners knowledgeable about the Learning Sites), to identify their needs/priorities;
- (iii) a consultation process with WP leaders, to identify the candidate information products to be developed in OBAMA-NEXT;
- (iv) a consultation process, by interviews and e-mail, with the PAB about the initial outcomes of ii-iii; and
- (v) a remote interactive meeting with PAB members involving the detailed discussion of the first four information products arising from the process.

Deliverable 1.1 represents the first step on the pathway for the completion of a set of information products, with an initial specification of the products to be developed by OBAMA-NEXT.

2. Background and objectives of the deliverable

Work Package (WP) 1 of OBAMA-NEXT is devoted to “Engagement of stakeholders and identification of product needs”. Hence, **the objectives of WP1 are:** (i) Engage stakeholders with complementary roles in marine policies through an approach that enables a dynamic interface (Task T1.1), (ii) for identifying and co-working on data needs (T1.2); (iii) towards meeting the expectations of the implementing authorities and fit for endorsement by policymakers (T1.3); and (iv) transferring generated knowledge and lessons learnt (T1.4).

The **Practitioners Advisory Board (PAB)** was built in T1.1 and **is composed by eight members**, including national competent authorities (Lotte Knudsen, Danish EPA; Rene Reisner, Estonian Ministry of Environment; Nir Stern, National Institute of Oceanography of Israel); Regional Seas Conventions (Christina Herbon, OSPAR/JNCC), experts from organizations and other European projects (Nicolas Pade, EMBRC; Jessica Junker, EuropaBON), and international institutions (Inga Lips, EuroGOOS; Paula Moschella, CIESM). After building the PAB, attention was placed to construct a process to **ensure (i) feedback** on the progress and activities performed, and (ii) **promote discussion**, transfer and uptake of intermediate project outcomes, which should be visible in a guideline/“design catalogue” that was developed and will be refined together with the PAB throughout the project’s implementation.

This catalogue was produced in T1.2 (Co-working and co-design process), by focusing on gathering requirements, starting with an exploration phase, identifying the problems to be addressed, share stakeholders’ needs and agree on the scope and specification of the information products, the end of **which resulted in the present Deliverable 1.1**. This phase received input through an online survey (Milestone M1.2), designed to identify the additional needs, to gather views and foster early discussions of the PAB. In a subsequent conception phase, the PAB and project partners will co-work responses and solutions to their identified needs. That phase will build on the complementary expertise of the group, making roles clear in the co-working process and safeguarding the commitment (in T1.3, with an iterative co-development and specification of data products). It is expected that this work will end in T1.4 (OBAMA-NEXT product guidelines and training of stakeholders), at the end of the project, through the production of a detailed specification and documentation of information products (D1.2) - in other words, a finalised version of the guidelines/design catalogue, including: (i) the data sources they should be compiled from, (ii) requirements for spatial and temporal resolution and coverage, (iii) potential challenges and associated issues/solutions for the development of the data and information products, and (iv) references. In addition to the detailed guidelines for practitioners, a policy brief that highlights the key take-home messages will be developed (D1.3).

Hence, Deliverable 1.1 represents the first step in the pathway for the e complete definition of the project products, beginning with the specification of the initial products to be developed by OBAMA-NEXT.

3. Process followed

To obtain an initial information product catalogue, which fulfils the societal/policy needs, we followed a structured approach, in order to receive the PAB's and other stakeholders' feedback. This helped us to shape the catalogue of products to be developed or refined during the project. Our approach involved the following steps:

- We made a PAB online survey on information products. This was completed as Milestone 1.2, and the results are included in Section 4.
- We extended the survey to some stakeholders nominated by the Learning Sites from the project, and the results are included in Section 5.
- From both surveys, we extracted the needs and expectations from the stakeholders. We included this information in Sections 4 and 5 and used it in the discussion section.
- We organized a consultation process with WP leaders, to identify the main products to be developed in OBAMA-NEXT, collating the specifications of the products in documents included in this deliverable, in Section 6.
- We made a consultation process with the PAB, about the initial list and results. That process used interviews and e-mail communication, which are collated in Section 7.
- With all this information, we organized a remote meeting for PAB consultation, using four initial products selected. The main results from this consultation are collated in Section 8.
- After all the above steps, we have concluded and recommended a way forward, in Section 9.

4. Practitioners Advisory Board survey and identification of needs

In April 2023, we organized an online survey for the eight members of the PAB, with the objective of checking their needs and expectations involving their participation in OBAMA-NEXT and the products to be developed by the project. The survey forms part of the basis of this D1.1 and was described in Milestone 1.2.

The survey report was structured in three parts (profile, needs and involvement), with an initial summary of the responses for each part, followed by a synthesis of the responses to each question. The complete survey, as well as an Excel file containing the responses, can be consulted in the OBAMA-NEXT Teams folder of Task 1.2 Co-working and co-design process:

<https://aarhusuniversitet.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/TECHOBAMANEXT/Delte%20dokumenter/General/WP1%20Stakeholder%20engagement/Task%201.2.%20Co-working%20and%20co-design%20process?csf=1&web=1&e=4m0CsA>

The following is a synthesis of the principal answers provided by the survey:

1. The profile: experienced respondents with higher education mostly working in national administration.

- Typology of respondents: 57.1% EU Member State, 42.9% national competent authority, 14.3% EU institutional body.
- Regional Sea in which they work: 14.3% Atlantic Ocean, 57.1% Baltic Sea, 14.3% Mediterranean Sea, 28.6% several regional seas.
- Type of stakeholder: 28.6% NGO, 42.9% national ministry of environment, 14.3% national competent authority, 14.3% research establishment.
- Experience in the field: 42.9% >20 years, 28.6% 11-20 years, 28.6% no response.
- Day-to-day work: 71.4% administration, 28.6% technical.
- Education level: 57.1% PhD, 42.9% MSc.

2. The needs: most of PAB members do not use monitoring tools and are little familiar with them. They currently use classical methods but consider applying High Frequency radars, eDNA, buoys, drones, citizen science and machine-learning. Satellites and ferry-boxes are already used, but new applications are expected.

For monitoring tools, the expectations are, among others: maximizing repeatability throughout time and space; reasonable affordability for operation and maintenance; ability to work autonomously for a long time-period; easy to use and easy to process large data sets; be cost-effective, non-invasive and scalable. Tools are used (or planned to be used) mainly for reporting within the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and Water Framework Directive (WFD), less in the context of Regional Seas Conventions (RSC), Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) and Birds and Habitats Directives (BHD), and much less in others (such as the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, UN Sustainable Development Goals, and EU Green Deal).

The major problems faced are lack of budget, coordination and spatial resolution. Lack of tools, temporal resolution and standardization was also mentioned, but not amongst the major challenges.

Need for numerical data (for species, communities, and habitats), data on temporal dynamics (species and communities) and spatial distribution (for species and habitats) was highlighted. Categorical data and categorical expert judgement data were also mentioned as needs when monitoring. Confidence measures, which are mostly quantitative, associated with the data are already in place and available.

Details of the responses:

- **Current use of monitoring tools:** 28.6% Yes, 57.1% No, 14.3% do not know.
- **Most important monitoring tools used:**
 - Commercial vessels to monitor diversity of soft bottom communities.
 - Remote sensing for physical oceanography.
 - eDNA metabarcoding to assess microbial or planktonic communities.
 - Plankton sampling campaigns using different nets.
 - Heavy metal monitoring in marine biota; hydrographic measurements - CTD (conductivity, temperature, depth + light, pH, oxygen and fluorescence).
 - Water chemistry/nutrients and plankton - sampling of seawater for subsequent analysis in the laboratory (nitrite/nitrate, ammonium, phosphate, silicate, total nitrogen, total phosphorus and chlorophyll + phyto- and zooplankton (species determination, numbers, biovolume, carbon content, primary production)).
 - Sediment chemistry and benthic fauna - sampling of sediment and subsequent analysis in lab (total nitrogen, total phosphorus, iron-bound phosphorus, dry matter, specific gravity, loss on ignition + for benthic fauna: species determination, numbers and biomass).
 - Macroalgae and macrophytes - surveys by divers and video.
 - Monitoring other species: acoustics (marine mammals) and aerial surveys (marine mammals and birds).
 - eDNA on non-indigenous species.
- **Familiarity with monitoring:** the respondents are familiar.
- **Novel monitoring tools their institution is considering incorporating:**
 - High Frequency radars to monitor surface currents.
 - eDNA methodology to assess marine and freshwater species diversity.
 - Mooring stations/buoys to collect all the available regional parameters (biology, chemistry and physics).
 - Drones.
 - Satellites (in use already but are like to be used for other purposes).
 - Citizen science.
 - Improved imaging (machine-learning).
 - Ferry-box (have been used earlier on).
- **Expectations from a marine monitoring tool:**
 - Minimize the environmental impact.
 - Maximize repeatability throughout time and space for the benefit of comparison with other regions.
 - Reasonable affordability for operation and maintenance.

- Ability to monitor spatially (not only spot-sampling).
- Ability to work autonomously for a long time-period (sufficient batteries, data storage capacity, data exchange, etc.) to reduce the maintenance costs.
- Standardised measurements to allow later co-use of collected data with other data collected by other monitoring methods or devices or tools, incl. parameters that are measured.
- Easy to use and easy to process large data sets.
- Precision, efficiency and opportunities for new monitoring subjects/organisms.
- Complementing traditional methods.
- Increase in spatio-temporal data coverage.
- Cost-effectiveness, non-invasive and scalable.
- **Monitoring tools for reporting under policy or legislative instruments:**
 - [Rank 1] 28.6% MSFD, 28.6% WFD.
 - [Rank 2] 28.6% MSFD, 14.3% WFD, 14.3% CFP.
 - [Rank 3] 28.6% BHD, 14.3% WFD, 14.3% BS.
 - [Rank 4] 28.6% RSC, 14.3% BHD.
 - [Rank 5] 14.3% CFP, 14.3% RSC, 14.3% BS.
 - [Rank 6] 14.3% BS.
 - [Rank 7] 14.3% SDG.
 - [Rank 8] 14.3% Green Deal.
- **Key issues faced when monitoring:**
 - [Rank 1] 28.6% budget, 28.6% coordination, 14.3% spatial.
 - [Rank 2] 28.6% lack tools, 14.3% spatial, 14.3% temporal, 14.3% standardization.
 - [Rank 3] 28.6% temporal, 14.3% standardization, 14.3% coordination.
 - [Rank 4] 28.6% budget, 14.3% spatial, 14.3% mismatch.
 - [Rank 5] 14.3% budget, 14.3% multiple, 14.3% inconsistency.
- **Type of data needed:**
 - [Numerical] 42.9% Y (species, communities, habitats), 57.1% N.
 - [Categorical] 100% N.
 - [Categorical expert judgement] 28.6% Y (species, habitats), 71.4% N.
 - [Temporal dynamics] 71.4% Y (species, communities), 28.6% N.
 - [Spatial distribution] 71.4% Y (species, habitats), 28.6% N.
- **Specific interest for information products:**
 - Habitat types and (protected) species listed in different EU legal acts (HD, MSFD, BD, proposed Nature Restoration Law) or other legislation (IUCN, HELCOM, OSPAR, etc.).
 - Also, info on (coastal and protected) fish species and important fish habitats needs improvement; macroalgae and macrophytes; plankton; fish (incl. bycatch); marine mammals (incl. bycatch); seabirds (incl. bycatch).
 - EuropaBON's Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBV) list here: <https://github.com/EuropaBON/EBV-Descriptions>

- **Confidence measures associated with your data:** 42.9% Y data, 14.3% Y expert, 14.3% Y multiple sources, 28.6% N (in these cases because they are not involved in monitoring). Comments on this answer:
 - Species diversity will be determined based on expert taxonomists for each taxon. We have confidence measures and evaluate the confidence of results when making status assessments. This covers following aspects as also in HELCOM status assessments (HOLAS): 1) data quality and reliability (incl., temporal and spatial coverage), 2) confidence of status classification system (e.g. thresholds set or not); 3) methodological confidence (standardised or not, regionally agreed or not, expert opinion, etc.). It follows standardized method. However, there are uncertainties with the collection of all data especially the highly mobile ones who which live hidden under the surface of the water most of the time and are spread over large areas, e.g. whales and some fish species.

3. The involvement: About half (42.9%) of respondents do not consider themselves as members of the PAB, even if the questionnaire was only sent to the eight PAB members. The most worrying is that 42.9 % of respondents do not want to be involved in the co-creation process, and 28.6% only want depending on the product and on their availability. If participating in the co-creation, respondents prefer mostly online meetings, surveys and emails, and less physical meetings. The preference is to be informed on the progress of work by e-mail, website, online meetings, and newsletters. The expectations from the co-creation process include better understanding of OBAMA-NEXT needs, usefulness of the cooperation for their own work, contribution to harmonize methods across Europe, and knowledge sharing.

Details of the responses:

- **Part of the PAB:** 57.1% Yes, 42.9% No.
- **Want to be involved in the co-creation process:** 28.6% Yes, 42.9% No, 28.6% conditional (in these cases, it depends on information product - for some research areas they are not able to provide input, and also depends on their availability).
- **Ways to participate in the co-creation process:**
 - [Rank 1] 14.3% physical, 28.6% online, 14.3% surveys.
 - [Rank 2] 14.3% physical, 14.3% online, 14.3% hybrid, 14.3% e-mail.
 - [Rank 3] 14.3% hybrid, 14.3% physical, 14.3% online.
 - [Rank 4] 14.3% email, 14.3% hybrid, 14.3% surveys.
 - [Rank 5] 14.3% individual, 14.3% email.
 - [Rank 6] 14.3% individual.
 - [Rank 7] 14.3% one to one.
- **Ways to be informed of the progress of the project:** e-mail, website, online meeting, newsletter.
- **Expectations from the co-creation process:**
 - Better understand the various needs that OBAMA-NEXT can answer and be exposed to new ideas and technologies to follow those needs.
 - Successful cooperation and usable results for own work.
 - That it can lead to the harmonization of methods between countries and the development of useful and relevant new tools.

- With opinions and input from different experts (including decision-makers), knowledge will be better shared and solutions to support different groups will be created.

5. Extended survey with Learning Sites-nominated stakeholders

In May and June 2023, we organized an online survey for the Learning Sites stakeholders, with the objective of obtaining information on their needs and expectations about their participation in OBAMA-NEXT and the products to be developed. It was sent to 24 stakeholders, but only 4 responded. The results are summarized below.

1. The profile: experienced respondents with higher education mostly working at national level either in administration or engaged in technical matters.

Typology of respondents: 50% EU Member State; 25% EU institutional body, working for only one country; and 25% EU institutional body, working for more than one country.

- **Regional Sea in which they work:** 50% North-East Atlantic; 50% Mediterranean Sea; 25% Baltic Sea; 25% Black Sea.
- **Type of stakeholder:** 50% ministry environment; 25% national competent authority; 25% other (intergovernmental marine research).
- **Experience in the field:** 25% >20 years; 25% 11-20 years; 25% 5-20 years; 25% no response.
- **Day-to-day work:** 75% technical and administration level; 25% administration.
- **Educational level:** 100% PhD.

2. The needs: half of respondents are currently using several monitoring tools e.g., eDNA, Underwater Visual Census (UVC) for fish and different organism groups. The expectations for marine monitoring tools are to be simple, cheap, provide suitable information and reliability. The respondents use (or want to use) tools mainly for reporting within the MSFD, less in the context of BHD, WFD, RSC, UN SDGs, EU Biodiversity Strategy (EBS). The major problems faced are the lack of sufficient budget and insufficient spatial coverage or resolution, as well as lack of monitoring tools and lack of coordination among Member States in the same regional sea. The respondents need mainly numerical data for species, communities, and habitats, pH and CO₂ (DIC) parameters; higher spatial and temporal resolution of existing parameters), spatial distribution (for species and habitats) data, temporal dynamics data (for species and habitats), and categorical expert judgements. Most of the respondents have confidence measures associated with their data.

Details of the responses:

- **Current use of monitoring tools:** 50% Yes, 50% No.
- **Most important monitoring tools that their institution is using:**
 - UVC for fish.
 - eDNA.
 - In situ sampling.
 - Sensors in deep waters, close to the seabed, to 'monitor' over time the trends in temperature and salinity.

- Arrival of exotic marine species through our extensive network of marine taxonomists, in relation to fishers.
- The frequency and extent of jellyfish outbreaks.
- Migrations of vulnerable seabird species, using miniature GPS.
- **Familiarity with monitoring:** one respondent is familiar, and one of them is not i.e. somebody else in the respondent institution uses them.
- **Expectations for a marine monitoring tool:**
 - Simple to handle.
 - Cheap to use.
 - Connected to data standards/database.
 - Provide information for assessing the ecological status of the marine ecosystem.
 - To check up the measures if they are appropriate or not for achieving GES.
 - EU-level database and data-viewer capabilities.
 - Database should be able to collect the data from existing databases in use in the regional seas conventions.
 - Reliability; robustness.
 - Repeatability across different users.
- **Monitoring tools for reporting under policy or legislative instruments:**
 - [Rank 1] 75% MSFD; 25% in my institution, we do not have reporting obligations related to marine monitoring.
 - [Rank 2] 25% BHD; 25% WFD; 25% RSCs.
 - [Rank 3] 25% BHD; 25% UN SDGs.
 - [Rank 4] 25% UN SDGs.
 - [Rank 5] 25% RSCs.
 - [Rank 6] 25% EU Biodiversity Strategy.
- **Key issues faced when monitoring:**
 - [Rank 1] 75% lack of budget to undertake monitoring; 25% insufficient spatial coverage or resolution.
 - [Rank 2] 50% lack of monitoring tools with reasonable cost to perform the activity; 25% lack of coordination among Member States in the same regional sea; 25% lack of budget to undertake monitoring.
 - [Rank 3] 50% lack of coordination among Member States in the same regional sea; 25% mismatch/incompleteness of data available with reporting obligations; 25% lack of monitoring tools with reasonable cost to perform the activity.
 - [Rank 4] 25% inconsistencies between datasets collected through different methodologies; 25% insufficient standardisation of methods for interoperability; 25% multiple institution dependency and coordination.
 - [Rank 5] 25% insufficient standardisation of methods for interoperability; 25% multiple institution dependency and coordination; 25% insufficient temporal coverage.
 - [Rank 6] 25% mismatch/incompleteness of data available with reporting obligations.
- **Other issues when monitoring** (1 response): lack of databases. In addition, a mismatch was indicated between the data you have available and your reporting obligations. Specification on which policy and

what type of data is missing (2 responses): problems arise from benthic habitats monitoring: lack of data to assess structure & functions; the MSFD and WFD reporting should be harmonized.

- **Type of data needed:**
 - [numerical] 100% yes (species; communities; habitats; pH and CO₂ (DIC) parameters; higher spatial and temporal resolution of existing parameters).
 - [Categorical] 25% yes (presence/absence of exotic species; presence/absence of threatened species (sharks); presence/absence of jelly fish outbreaks).
 - [Categorical expert judgement] 25% yes.
 - [Temporal dynamics] 50% yes (species; habitats).
 - [Spatial distribution] 50% yes (species; habitats).
- **Specific interest for information products:**
 - Non-commercial fish (squalls, etc.);
 - Benthic habitats: soft bottom, deep sea.
 - Sessile marine species of HD.
 - All because they are part of Descriptors – MSFD.
- **Confidence measures associated with your data:** 50 % yes, based on expert judgement (e.g., ‘high’ or ‘low’); 25% yes, based on data analyses (e.g., variance); 25% no. Comments on this answer:
 - No: no methodology to assess it => sometimes expert judgement.
 - Yes: 1) expert judgment is very important in evaluation and validation of data; 2) confidence is assessed in the regional seas conventions in the HOLAS III and QSR2023 products; 3) our data are integrated in our databases only after validation by our local experts (taxonomists, oceanographers, etc) to avoid risk of database contamination.

3. The involvement: only one respondent is part of the PAB and is not sure how he or she would want to be involved in the co-creation process. The respondent is willing to participate in the co-creation process preferably by online survey and then through e-mail communication and would prefer to be informed of the progress of the project through e-mail as well.

- **Part of the PAB:** 75% no; 25% yes.
- **Want to be involved in the co-creation process:** 25% it depends, not specified.
- **Ways to participate in the co-creation process:**
 - [Rank 1] 25% by online surveys.
 - Rank 2] 25% through e-mail communication.
- **Ways to be informed of the progress of the project:**
 - [Rank 1] 25% through e-mail communication.

6. Consultation to Work Package leaders and identification of products

6.1. The process

WP1 leaders developed the template for the proposed information products and contacted leads of WPs 2-6, with a request to encourage the WP leads to consider proposing a candidate information product through the completion of the template data fields. Both already operational products tested/applied at local/regional scales were included, together with those yet at the concept stage, but potentially of interest and therefore worth to be consulted with PAB.

6.2. The template

The template used to collate information products can be seen below. It is a simple description of the product intended to be developed, along with the name of the policy to which it can be addressed, as well as some indications on spatial and temporal resolution and current state of development.

1	Name of the data product	
2	Short description of the data product (e.g., human-induced stressor, ecosystem component, organism group or other; max. 50 words)	
3	Name of the policy/legislative instrument and the relevant detailed provision	
4	Data product type	
5	Data product format or data unit (<i>If not applicable to product please indicate with N/A</i>)	
6	Spatial resolution (<i>If not applicable to product please indicate with N/A</i>)	
7	Temporal resolution (<i>If not applicable to product please indicate with N/A</i>)	
8	Scale of spatial application (local/national/regional/international; please provide indication of location if/as appropriate)	
9	Current state of development (concept/in development/operational):	

6.3. The outcome

Annex 10.2 provides information on the **18 proposed information products by OBAMA-NEXT** scientists. Amongst others, it highlights the status (i.e. the maturity stage) of the information product, which is important for the discussions with the PAB. The candidate information products, as well as their current status, are:

1. Seagrass mapping – distributions and ecological status: in development or semioperational proposal.
2. Coastal vegetation mapping – upscaled from drones to satellites: development of the concept proposal initiated.

3. Suitability maps for seagrass restoration/repopulation: concept proposal.
4. Quantification of habitat carbon sequestration: development of the concept proposal initiated.
5. Cyanobacteria bloom: concept proposal.
6. eDNA species distribution maps: concept proposal.
7. eDNA run-off bioindicators: concept proposal.
8. Fish distribution model/map: concept proposal.
9. Position paper on eDNA use for stakeholders: concept proposal.
10. Population estimates of seabirds based on drone images and object recognition: in development or semioperational proposal.
11. Population estimates of sea mammals based on drone images and object recognition: in development or semioperational proposal.
12. Phytoplankton functional type map: concept proposal.
13. Data- and criteria-based identification of HD habitat types: development of the concept proposal initiated.
14. Underwater biodiversity hotspot map: operational proposal.
15. A map for allocating human activities at sea (e.g. offshore wind power): in development or semioperational proposal.
16. Hypoxia map for marine areas: in development or semioperational proposal.
17. Spatial distribution models for threatened species: operational proposal.
18. In-situ observation of phytoplankton blooms: operational proposal.

7. Consultation with the PAB regarding the initial list of information products

7.1. Introduction

An individual-based approach was applied to seek feedback from PAB on the information products considered by the project. Two separate communication-lines were applied:

1. Formal e-mail communication on the feedback on the 18 proposed products by OBAMA-NEXT scientists
2. Phone/Teams communication on the extended 'shopping list' detailing the various taxa/methodologies etc. feeding into the further development of the currently existing 18 products.

7.2. Outcomes of the formal communication

PAB members provided the following feedback (by e-mail) in June 2023:

- In general: *"It would be good to have an indication of whether the service is an idea from the consortium or if it is responding to an explicit request from a stakeholder. In the case of the latter, they should be priority"*.
- Coastal vegetation mapping – upscaled from drones to satellites: *"This seems to be an important up-scaling of the first service offered and would be really useful at a larger scale of monitoring and planning. This should be considered a priority to develop, in my opinion"*.
- Quantification of habitat carbon sequestration: *"C storage is very topical and needed for good management and conservation. There are A LOT of blue carbon initiatives going about and you should be linking with other projects dedicated to BC to see what can already be picked up from other projects or contributed to other projects. IT would be good to have some agreement on how to do things rather than 16 different solutions to the same task"*.
- Cyanobacteria bloom product: *"Again, it is not clear what in situ data will be used. Ground truthing of satellite products are an important service to develop I think, considering the challenges of accurate remote sensing in coastal waters"; "This should be a higher priority due to importance of establishing good ground-truthing for remote sensing products"*.
- eDNA species distribution maps: Clarify if they are *"species to be identified/prioritised"*; *"Mapping and occurrence are key to establishing MPAs and in the past many sites were rejected due to a lack of information and data. This should be a high priority. IT is also a task that is common to many projects, and I wonder if this would be better served as a larger exercise, rather than project specific? At least there should be an effort to put the information in the same place to ensure people can use data from many initiatives to construct the maps"*.
- eDNA runoff bioindicators: *"There is a lot to be done on this topic. There is a WP in MARCO-BOLO similar to this and links could be made to concentrate efforts. Identifying a couple of freshwater products would be good as this area is lacking behind in my understanding"*.
- Fish distribution model/map: *"Are this sort of products not already available from ICES? Should ICES be involved in the development?"*.
- Position paper on eDNA use for stakeholders: *"Proposed inter-project activity, and very worthwhile!"*
- Suitability maps for seagrass restoration: *"This will be determined based on what? It is a great addition to the other seagrass services but not clear how the analysis will be conducted, based on what information?"*

- Phytoplankton functional type map: *“Considering the potential importance of knowing function over different seasons, this is well worth developing as a priority. Its use also goes beyond just the mapping.”*
- Data- and criteria-based identification of HD habitat types: specify criteria and data. *“The details are pretty sparse for a concept already in development. More details would be welcome”.*
- Underwater biodiversity hotspot maps: *“This would be worth demonstrating using data from another country to show it really works”.*
- A map for allocating human activities at sea (e.g. offshore wind power): *“What is the data source for this?”.*
- Hypoxia map for marine areas: *“I am guessing the explanation on how this will be done is missing?”; “Would it make sense then to work towards automated methods, where a data workflow will ingest the relevant data specified and prepare the map, rather than a case-by-case basis?”*

7.3. Outcomes of phone/Teams communication

The following points/issues were raised during the individual communications with selected PAB members:

- Citizen science as a method should be encouraged and therefore, information products benefitting input from this method should be given emphasis,
- In some regional seas in Europe, elevated frequency and magnitude of mass mortality of several marine species is an increasing issue. The information product on observing and documenting mass mortalities of marine organisms is therefore of interest for PAB members,
- While several MSFD descriptors are relatively well covered, some deserve further attention and need properly documented evidence. One of those is D4 (foodwebs), for which one or more information products should be considered to be developed,
- It was commented that benthic macrofauna is quite comprehensively addressed in the planned work through multiple parameters to be likely developed. It was suggested to consider applying the parameters proposed for the benthic macrofauna to other marine organisms,
- Applications combining different approaches in biodiversity studies was mentioned as being of interest:
 - Microscopy and flow-cam in phytoplankton studies,
 - Models combining data from acoustic and trawling surveys, observations and tagging information in studies on elasmobranchs,
- Two comments on inclusion of species/communities were specifically made. These were:
 - Hard bottom community (rocky shore invertebrates and algae) diversity and distribution
 - Tuna, including via contacting ICCAT,
- Application of several methodological approaches was discussed and suggested to be further elaborated/applied for particular organism groups. These are:
 - eDNA for pelagic fish,
 - Visual censuses (rapid survey assessment) for fish and hard bottom community,
 - Hydrophone surveys for small cetaceans,
 - Census on ships for birds.

8. Remote meeting with the PAB to discuss selected information products

The following **four products**, in different stages of development, **were selected** for presentation and further discussions to hear PAB feedback:

- **Quantification of habitat carbon sequestration:** development of the concept proposal initiated.
- **Population estimates of seabirds based on drone images and object recognition:** in development or semioperational proposal.
- **Underwater biodiversity hotspot map:** operational proposal.
- **Spatial distribution models for threatened species:** operational proposal.

The differences in the stage of development were consciously selected to have the opportunity to interact and co-create with the PAB at different stages, during the life of the project.

8.1. Agenda and contents of the meeting

The online meeting took place **October 23rd, 14-16 CET and was attended by six PAB members**, WP1 core team, and the project coordinator. The meeting was facilitated by two AAU researchers, Maurizio Teli and Josefin Ekstedt, and had the following agenda:

- 14:00 – 14:10 - General introduction and welcome.
- 14:10 – 14:35 - Short presentations of the four information products (five minutes each): Spatial distribution models for threatened species; Underwater biodiversity hotspot map; Population estimates of seabirds based on drone images and object recognition; Quantification of habitat Carbon sequestration.
- 14:35 – 14:40 - Introduction to Breakout Rooms and collaborative work.
- 14:40 – 15:05 - First Breakout Rooms round: Collaborative User Journey on “Population estimates of seabirds based on drone images and object recognition”; Collaborative Scenario Writing on “Spatial distribution models for threatened species”.
- 15:05 – 15:10 - Break
- 15:10 – 15:35 - Second Breakout Rooms round: Collaborative Scenario Writing on “Quantification of habitat carbon sequestration”; Collaborative User Journey on “Underwater biodiversity hotspot map”.
- 15:35 – 16:00 - Plenary discussion (including feedback on the session).

As it can be noticed, techniques coming from Co-Design and Interaction Design has been adopted for two rounds of breakout rooms, Collaborative User Journey and Collaborative Scenario Writing. They were facilitated through a specific Miro board, with the intention to trigger conversations connecting the information products to the practice of monitoring marine ecosystems and biodiversity. Other than the Miro board, the meeting was conducted via Aarhus University instance of Microsoft Teams, with the meeting recorded automatically, and four breakout rooms were created, one per each information product. Allocation of PAB members to the specific breakout rooms took place during the meeting, after the presentations of the four products, and the allocation

followed the preferences of the participants, collected in real time. PAB members had been asked to provide their consent to audio and video recording via the calendar invitation, and the developers of the information products had been asked to share their presentations in advance.

8.2. Analysis of the meeting

The meeting results have gone through a preliminary analysis that relied on the automatic transcriptions of the audio conversations generated by MS Teams and the textual content of the Miro board used during the meeting. The texts have been uploaded to NVivo 13 and coded inductively by Maurizio Teli. The axis along which the conversation unfolded was organizational and ecological.

When referring to **organizational elements**, one issue stood out as key, the issue of costs, not only monetary (e.g. the cost of the hardware itself, as with drones) but related to the implication of monitoring for other practices, like fishing. Another organizational element that emerged was labour power with specific characteristics, for example the importance of pilots for drones or of citizen scientists to supplement available data. The way in which the presentations covered what kind of data are collected was mostly sufficient, with some specific clarifications needed on specific products, pointing to the expertise that the PAB members have on the measurement provided by the different information products. In general, the organizational elements were relevant for the PAB members to get deeper in understanding through which working practices the information provided are collected.

Regarding the **ecological elements**, the emphasis was on the kind of species or habitats the data presented, as well as how the data help connect with different framework directives at the policy level, and how the models have been built to derive the visualizations of the information products. Attention was also devoted to the capacity of the information products to adapt to different habitats, different species, or different weather conditions, for example. This is probably the key result of the meeting, according to the preliminary analysis conducted: the inquiries of the PAB were related to what we can call a **flexible relation between organizational and ecological elements**. The PAB was interested in how flexible the different information products are in terms of new observations, especially in relation to different habitats, and how consistent the quality of the data are for different species, locations, and organizational conditions.

9. Conclusions, recommendations and way forward

The survey to both the PAB members and the local stakeholders, provided a broad view of their expectations and needs in relation to the project's future developments. Some of the most important needs were that any product developed should maximize repeatability throughout time and space; have reasonable affordability for operation and maintenance; have ability to work autonomously for a long time-period; be easy to use and easy to process large data sets; be cost-effective, non-invasive and scalable. The stakeholders also highlighted the need of numerical data for species, communities, and habitats, data on temporal dynamics (species and communities) and spatial distribution (for species and habitats).

With these expectations in mind, members of OBAMA-NEXT, working in different tasks from WP2-6, decided on 18 products to be prioritized in the project, covering different ecosystem components, including both species and habitats, as well as pelagic and benthic systems. The 18 products were classified in different levels of development, from only at the concept stage (7 products), to initial development (3 products), in development or semi-operational (5 products) and being fully operational (3 products).

The consultation to members of the PAB, provided useful insights the product developers of each WP for improving or responding to the demands and needs of future end-users.

In the same way, the final plenary of the meeting of October 23rd gave a positive assessment of the meeting but also indications on rethinking the way the conversations in breakout rooms took place. In the debriefing session that followed the meeting, Maurizio Teli and Josefin Ekstedt agreed that the prompt triggered a conversation but didn't structure it, suggesting that the format should be rethought in relation to the feedback the PAB members, as well as the time constraints. Nevertheless, all PAB members attending expressed interest in attending future meetings. This encourages the Consortium to continue its co-design and co-development activities with adjustments to the format. Regarding the future development of information products, the PAB suggested a focus on products, which can be adjusted outside of its original context of design and development, and how that entails attention to both organizational and ecological aspects.

Hence, with this Deliverable 1.1:

- We have an initial specification of 18 information products fulfilling policy needs.
- The overview of expectations and needs of the PAB members and stakeholders should be considered by the scientists working at the different WPs to improve the specifications of the products.
- The organization of remote, short (2-2.5 hours) and dynamic meetings with PAB members and product developers, to present the status and capacities of the products, has been demonstrated as a useful tool to receive feedback in the process of co-creation. On this basis, it has been decided to organize regular (e.g. every 4 months) meetings to present and discuss new products or the progress of products already presented.

10. Annexes

10.1. Questionnaire to the PAB

Dear Participant,

we would like to extend a warm welcome to you and thank you for taking the time to participate in this survey promoted by the Horizon Europe OBAMA-NEXT project. As a professional in this field, your input is critical in helping us gain insights on the problems to be addressed in the observation and mapping of marine ecosystems and on your needs as a stakeholder in the field. This will help us refine the requirements, in terms of scope and specification, of the information products that OBAMA-NEXT aims at providing you with.

In fact, OBAMA-NEXT is a project funded by the European Commission (G.A. 101081642) that aims to develop a toolbox for generating and collating accurate, precise and relevant information characterizing marine ecosystems and their biodiversity. The project includes 22 partner organizations based in 15 different countries in Europe, and it includes a Practitioners Advisory Board, to which this survey is sent too. As for now, the Practitioners Advisory Board includes representatives of competent national authorities, international institutions, regional sea conventions, and other research projects.

This survey is one of the first steps of the co-creation activities the partners of OBAMA-NEXT are conducting to “identify the policy and societal needs and guide the product development” of the overall project. The results of the survey will be presented during an online workshop that will be held between August and September 2023. The workshop will involve the members of the Practitioners Advisory Board and other people who would express their interest into it. For OBAMA-NEXT, the overall goal of this initial part is to prioritize the development of information products, for which we now have 17 candidates (available in the appendix to this survey, if you are interested in skimming through them).

The survey is structured in three parts: (1) Basic Information, (2) Monitoring Needs and Tools Features, and (3) Engagement in the Co-Creation Process. It should take you approximately 15-20 minutes to complete it.

The questionnaire is strictly anonymous, the respondent is not identified when answering the questionnaire, and no answer is associated with the respondent.

We thank you for taking the time to answer this survey,

Ángel Borja, Henn Ojaveer, Maurizio Teli, and Rowana Walton for the OBAMA- NEXT Consortium

Section A: Part I. Basic information

*Mandatory

***A1. Are you representing or working with...**

[multiple choice]

- The government of an EU Member State, Accession Country or Norway
- Other country
- An institutional body (e.g. National Competent Authorities), working for only one country
- An institutional body, working for more than one country (e.g., DG-ENV, EEA, RSCs)
- I am not representing or working with any particular country
- Other (please specify):

***A2. What is(are) the Regional Sea(s) you are most involved with?**

[multiple choice]

- North-East Atlantic
- Baltic Sea
- Black Sea
- Mediterranean Sea
- Overseas territories
- Arctic
- All European seas
- Other geographic region (please specify):

***A3. Which of these types of stakeholders and/or organisation better describes your role?**

[choose one]

- Ministry of Environment representative or similar (administration level)
- National Competent Authority (technical level)
- European Commission or Agency
- Regional Sea Convention
- Non-Governmental Organisation
- For-profit private company
- Other, please specify:

***A4. For how many years have you been working in the marine monitoring field?**

[choose one]

- >20 years
- 11-20 years
- 5-10 years

- <5 years

***A5. Which is the best description for your day-to-day work?**

[choose one]

- I work mostly at a technical/scientific level (e.g., monitoring, assessment)
- I work mostly at an administrative level (e.g., coordination, organisation, supervision)
- I work both at a technical and administrative level

***A6. In OBAMA-NEXT, we define as tools for monitoring all instruments used to collect first-hand information on marine ecosystems and their biodiversity. If the work of your institution entails marine monitoring, does your institution already use specific tools for monitoring?**

[choose one]

- No, it is not the role of my institution to undertake monitoring
- No, at my institution we do not use any specific tools
- I do not know if my institution uses any specific tools
- My institution itself does not use the tool(s) others perform the monitoring with a mandate from the institution
- Yes, at my institution we use marine monitoring tool(s)

A7. As others perform monitoring activities for your institution, do you know if they use specific tools? [Only if you answered (A6): My institution itself does not use the tool(s) others perform the monitoring with a mandate from the institution.]

[choose one]

- I do not know if they use or they do not use tools.
- I am aware they use one or more tools

A8. You mentioned that others are performing monitoring activities for your institution. Please list which tools they use. [Only if you answered (A7): I am aware they use one or more tools.]

[open answer]

A9. You mentioned that your institution uses specific monitoring tools. List the 5 most important monitoring tools your institution currently uses [Only if you answered (A6): yes, at my institution we use marine monitoring tool(s)]

[open answer]

A10. How familiar are you with the tools you just listed? [Only if you answered (A6): yes, at my institution we use marine monitoring tool(s)]

[choose one]

- I perform monitoring / I use the tool(s)
- I am familiar with them (I know how they work, but I do not use them)

- Somebody else in my institution uses them

A11. Please list at least 3 novel monitoring tools that your institution is considering incorporating. [Only if you answered (A6): yes, at my institution we use marine monitoring tool(s)]

[open answer]

***A12. Which is the maximum level of formal education you have achieved?**

[choose one]

- High school
- Bachelor degree
- Master degree
- PhD

Section B: Part II. Monitoring Needs and Tools Features

***B1. What do you expect from a marine monitoring tool? Indicate the three top features or capacities that such a tool should have and why.**

[open answer]

***B2. Are you looking for marine monitoring tools that can support your institution in implementing or reporting under policy or legislative instruments? If yes, please indicate which ones, and please rank them accordingly.**

Please select at least 5 answers and rank them according to their importance (1 most important).

- Marine Strategy Framework Directive
- Birds and Habitats Directives
- Water Framework Directive
- Common Fisheries Policy
- Regional Seas Conventions
- European Biodiversity Strategy
- UN Sustainable Development Goals
- Green Deal
- In my institution, we do not have reporting obligations related to marine monitoring

***B3. What are the key issues that you face when it comes to the marine monitoring?**

Please select up to 5 statements and rank them according to their importance (1 most important).

- Lack of coordination among Member States in the same regional sea
- Lack of budget to undertake monitoring
- Lack of monitoring tools with reasonable cost to perform the activity
- Insufficient spatial coverage or resolution

- Insufficient temporal coverage
- Mismatch/incompleteness of data available with reporting obligations
- Insufficient standardisation of methods for interoperability
- Multiple institution dependency and coordination
- Inconsistencies between datasets collected through different methodologies
- Other issues

B4. If you selected other issues in your top 5 (B3), please specify any other relevant aspects that you can think of.

[open answer]

B5. If you indicated a mismatch between the data you have available and your reporting obligations (B3). Can you specify which policy this is and what type of data are you missing?

[open answer]

***B6. In general, what type of data do you need/want and you don't have access to? Please indicate if you need these data for 1. species, 2. communities or 3. habitats. Comment only if you choose an answer. [multiple choice]**

- Numerical
 - Comment:
- Categorical
 - Comment:
- Categorical expert judgement
 - Comment:
- Temporal dynamics
 - Comment:
- Spatial distribution
 - Comment:
- Other, please specify:
 - Comment:

B7. Please indicate any species, communities, or habitats of specific interest for information products.

[open answer]

***B8. Do you have confidence measures associated with your data (i.e., how confident are you about the data collected)?**

[choose one]

- No

- Yes, based on data analyses (e.g., variance)
- Yes, based on expert judgement (e.g. 'high' or 'low')
- Yes, from multiple sources depending on parameter(s)

***B9. Please explain why there are no confidence measures available. [Only if you answered (B8): no]**

[open answer]

***B10. Please, comment on the answer you provided. [Only if you answered (B8): yes,....]**

[open answer]

Section C: Part III. Engagement in the co-creation process

With co-creation in OBAMA-NEXT, we refer to a collaborative process where ideas are continuously shared between practitioners and project partners and improved together. By adopting this approach, we consider the involvement of the policymakers and the key stakeholders central from beginning, i.e. the early selection and priority of products to be developed or refined. In this way, we aim to optimize developments, increase efficiency of implementation and provide legitimacy to the outputs created, i.e. validity within the targeted policies' context and stakeholders needs. A co-creation process makes it more likely that all parties feel a co-ownership of the solutions generated and, in this part of the survey, we inquire how much you would like to be involved in such a process. If you agree to be further involved, we will invite you to an online workshop in August or September 2023, where we will present our elaboration of the results of this survey and the future steps. In all cases, your participation is considered voluntary, and you can step back at any time you would consider it necessary for you.

***C1. Are you part of the OBAMA-NEXT Practitioners Advisory Board (PAB)?**

[choose one]

- Yes
- No

C2. Do you want to be involved in the OBAMA-NEXT co-creation process of the development of information products?

- No
- Yes
- It depends. Please specify...

From now on only answer if you selected "yes" or "it depends, please specify..." in question C2.

C3. In which ways would you be willing to participate in this co-creation process? Select up to five modalities, ranking them according to your preferences.

Select your preferences from the options below, even more than one.

- Physical meetings
- One to one annual conversations

- Online meetings, e.g. online workshops
- Hybrid meeting e.g., attend project meetings remotely if relevant
- Through e-mail communication
- By online surveys
- Through individual or focus group interviews (in person or online)

***C4. How would you like to be informed of the progress of the project?**

Select your preferences from the options below.

- Through e-mail communication
- I would like to be informed directly (by email) on the progress only if my input is needed
- Through the project website
- Through a dedicated newsletter
- Through briefing online meetings/webinars
- Other. Please specify...

***C5. What do you expect from this co-creation process?**

[open answer]

We thank you for taking the time to answer this survey!

10.2. Initial list of products

Proposed information products to achieve D1.1 "Initial specification information product catalogue fulfilling societal/policy need" Red: concept, Yellow: concept starting development, Green: in development or semioperational, Blue: operational

Name of the data product	Seagrass mapping – distributions and ecological status	Coastal vegetation mapping – upscaled from drones to satellites	Suitability maps for seagrass restoration/repopulation	Quantification of habitat carbon sequestration	Cyanobacteria bloom	eDNA species distribution maps	eDNA run-off bioindicators	Fish distribution model/map	Position paper on eDNA use for stakeholders
Short description of the data product	Drone-based seagrass mapping, including <i>in situ</i> ground truthing, model training (ML), testing and validation	- Fusion of high-resolution, small scale drone data and lower-resolution, large scale satellite images for upscaling of coastal vegetation maps (macroalgae, seagrass, bivalves, etc.). - Protocols explaining standards for this method	Suitability maps for seagrass restoration (active restoration) to be used also in combination with other initiatives involving passive restoration (i.e. spatial protection measures) and maps of possible donor populations of healthy seagrass (see product #1).	Mapping ecosystem services (carbon sequestration) by combining species distribution maps, habitats mapping, and <i>in situ</i> measurements (e-DNA, DOC, POC) to assess the ecosystem carbon sequestration capabilities	Integration of <i>in situ</i> , satellite and flow cytometry for cyanobacteria bloom forecast	Maps of NIS, rare, toxic, pathogenic, emblematic/rare protected species based on eDNA findings. List of species must be co-constructed between experts and stakeholders	Bioindicators of river run-off inputs from land, including potential pathogens, toxic species, terrestrial species	Map or statistical distribution map of fish species distribution in coastal offshore waters based on the comparison of different techniques (eDNA/bioacoustics/field data)	This paper will provide a table that states if and how eDNA could answer to stakeholder formalised needs
Name of the policy/legislative instrument and the relevant detailed provision	HD, MSFD, WFD reporting; European Biodiversity Strategy (identification of MPA target attainment), GBF (30/30)	MSFD, WFD reporting; European Biodiversity Strategy (identification of MPA target attainment, biodiversity-rich habitats, carbon-rich habitats)	GBF (30/30), EU Biodiversity Strategy (biodiversity-rich habitats and blue carbon habitats), future Nature Restoration Law	Blue Carbon	WFD	MSFD, MPA	MSFD	MSFD	Different according to stakeholders needs
Data product type	- Maps of seagrass, their status (coverage, distribution, shoot density, perhaps also canopy height, diversity and maximum depth distribution) and temporal trends of these. - Maps of potential donor populations for seagrass restoration (see product #3).	Coastal vegetation classification maps and trends (see also product #1)	Suitability map (e.g., geoTIFF) for seagrass restoration (and donor meadows)	Classification of ecosystem C storage	Forecast of cyanobacteria bloom	Distribution map	Relative abundance of Indicator species	Distribution model in relative abundance	Formalised expert opinion
Data product format or data unit	- Georeferenced images/maps (e.g., geoTIFF), data unit is seagrass classes and/or quality status - Protocols for standardized data collection (drone data and ground truth data) and analyses. - Contributions to EOVS and EBVs.	Georeferenced images (e.g., geoTIFF), data unit is habitat type	Georeferenced images, data unit is potential areas for repopulation of seagrass	C storage, mgCcm-2	bloom classification	Number of sites with species detection/% abundance	% of impacted river outlet and degree of impact	% of species abundances	N/A
Spatial resolution	Pixel size at cm scale	Pixel size 10-100 m	10-100 m	Spatial resolution of the underlying data	spatial resolution of the underlie data	Europe	Europe	Europe	N/A
Temporal resolution	Product covering the campaign duration, typically hours/days. Could also be repeated daily, weekly, monthly, yearly.	5-10 days (depending on satellite frequency)	N/A	N/A	5-10 days	Depending of species biology	Annual, depending of river flow	Annual	N/A
Scale of spatial application (local/national/regional/international; please provide indication of location if/as appropriate)	Local / regional (but could be scaled up – see product #2)	Regional / National / Europe	Regional / National	Local / Regional	Local / Regional	Europe	Europe	Europe	Europe, depending of stakeholders representants
Current state of development (concept/in development/operational):	In development (SeaBee/NIVA-Norway). Also considered developed as part of an OBAMA-NEXT coherent mapping study across Learning Sites.	Concept. Also considered developed as part of an OBAMA-NEXT coherent mapping study across Learning Sites.	Concept	Concept (but see Frigstad et al. 2021 , Kvile et al. 2022 , Gundersen et al. 2022 for Norway and other Nordic countries)	Concept	concept	concept	concept	concept

Name of the data product	Population estimates of seabirds based on drone images and object recognition (AI/ML)	Population estimates of sea mammals based on drone images and object recognition (AI/ML)	Phytoplankton functional type map	Data- and criteria-based identification of HD habitat types	Underwater biodiversity hotspot map	A map for allocating human activities at sea (e.g. offshore wind power)	Hypoxia map for marine areas	Spatial distribution models for threatened species	In-situ observation of phytoplankton blooms
Short description of the data product	Population estimates of seabird colonies, including information on species, age, sex, nesting status, and feeding activity. To replace ineffective methods using airplanes and manual bird counting.	Population estimates of sea mammals (e.g., seals), including information on species, age, sex, and activity patterns. To replace ineffective methods using vessels and manual counting.	Maps of the phytoplankton functional types determined by flow cytometry data and EO data	Habitat-complex types <i>sensu</i> the EC Habitats Directive – identified and mapped based on data and criteria	A map depicting areas of high ecological or biological value	A map of sea areas with low ecological value, suitable for development of human activities. Can also take into account profitability	A map showing sea areas that are prone for hypoxia; based	A map projecting distribution areas of rare or threatened marine species (e.g., species listed in EU habitats directive Annex II).	Real-time observations of harmful algal blooms using ships-of-opportunity
Name of the policy/legislative instrument and the relevant detailed provision	EU Birds Directive, MSFD	N/A	MSFD, WFD	Habitats Directive (HD) reporting and Natura 2000 network establishment/assessment	EU Biodiversity strategy 2030: information for planning '30 by 30' (development of the marine protected area network) and '10 % strict' (determining where strictly protected areas should be placed).	Maritime Spatial Planning directive; developing sustainable Blue Economy: ecosystem-based allocation of human activities (e.g., offshore wind).	-MSFD: Spatial allocation of actions mitigating eutrophication, in particular regulating land-based nutrient sources. -EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030: Placing in-situ restoration actions.	Habitats directive: focusing field studies to locate occurrences of endangered species and proposing establishment of Natura 2000 areas to protect them.	MSFD: Detailed information on the occurrence and strength of harmful algal blooms (e.g., cyanobacteria and toxic dinoflagellates) can be used for assessing effectiveness of MSFD measures aiming to mitigate eutrophication
Data product type	Georeferenced images and maps, data unit is species and population size.	Georeferenced images and maps, data unit is species and population size.	Distribution map	Maps	A map depicting sea areas with highest ecological and biological value. Based on species distribution modelling; can consider all "values" on which data exists, such as rare and threatened species, functionally important species, fish reproduction areas, special areas for birds, etc.	A map, produced with Zonation Programme, depicting sea areas that are the most suitable for placing a given human activity, such as offshore wind power. Based on spatial modelling of nature values (see information product type X), human interest, as well as economic profitability of deploying the given human activity.	A map showing the sea areas that are prone to hypoxia.	Several maps, based on statistical modelling, showing probable occurrences of threatened species.	on species composition and biomass of phytoplankton/cyanobacteria communities along a ship line crossing a sea basin
Data product format or data unit	N/A	N/A	NCDF file containing raster file with 300m pixel size containing concentration of relevant phytoplankton functional types		A raster map produced with Zonation software. Polygons can be drawn to depict the most valuable areas in a simplified format.	A raster map. Polygons can be drawn to depict the most suitable areas in a simplified format.	Raster. The map can be thresholded using selected limits of anoxia and hypoxia.	A raster map, produced with statistical species distribution modelling (SDM) methods.	Spatially and temporally explicit data on (i) biomasses of different algae, from flow-through measurements of chlorophyll-a and other pigments; and (ii) species information, from water samples collected from the flow-through.
Spatial resolution	N/A	N/A	300 m to 1 km	To be decided Min: 500 x 500m Max: In some case 100 x 100m	Depends on resolution of available data; e.g. for the entire Finnish sea area available in 20x20 m resolution.	Depends on resolution of available data; for decision-making purposes relevant resolution 0.1–1.0 km.	Depends on the available resolution of the local bathymetry map. For Finland, produced at 20 m resolution. For the purpose of allocating mitigation actions, 0.1-1.0 km resolution sufficient.	Depends on resolution of available data. E.g., for the entire Finnish sea area available in 20x20 m resolution.	As determined for the flow-through sampler (e.g., 500 m).
Temporal resolution	Potentially e.g., daily, weekly, monthly, or yearly.	Potentially e.g., daily, weekly, monthly, or yearly.	Daily (source), seasonal and yearly (composite)	N/A	One map depicts one moment in time, depending on the available data. If scenarios for relevant parameters are available, projections can be made for the future, or the past.	Maps depict one moment in time, usually present day. If scenarios for relevant parameters (e.g., environmental conditions, nature values, costs of building) exist, can also be made for the future.	The map depicts one moment in time, normally the present day.	Maps depict one moment in time, usually present day. If scenarios for relevant parameters (e.g., environmental conditions, nature values, costs of building) exist, can also be made for the future.	As determined for the flow-through sampler: minutes to hours.
Scale of spatial application (local/national/regional/international; please provide indication of location if/as appropriate)	Local / regional	Local / regional	Regional: Celtic Sea/Bristol Channel; English Channel/south of North Sea; Baltic Dea; Gulf of Naples	LS 2 Kattegat (potentially also other Learning Sites)	Can be made for any spatial scale for which spatial data exist, e.g., a specific sea basin, sea area of a nation, a regional sea, or all European sea areas.	Can be made for any spatial scale for which spatial data exist, e.g., a specific sea basin, sea area of a nation, a regional sea, or all European sea areas.	Can in theory be prepared for any spatial scale for which data exist, e.g., a specific sea area, a regional sea, or all European sea areas. Most relevant for fragmented coastal and archipelago areas that are prone to hypoxia due to topographic reasons.	Can be made for any spatial scale for which spatial data exist, e.g., a specific sea basin, sea area of a nation, a regional sea, or all European sea areas.	Depends on the route of the ship-of-opportunity: sea basin, or an entire regional sea.
Current state of development (concept/in development/operational):	Under development within the SeaBee drone infrastructure.	Under development within the SeaBee drone infrastructure.	concept	Concept, an operational tool will be developed and demonstrated in LS2	Operational for one nation (Finland). Reference for the MPA planning: DoI 10.3389/fmars.2018.00402/full	Semi-operational: methods available, but each case needs to be prepared individually. Reference for placing offshore wind in Finland: 10.1016/j.rser.2022.112087	Semi-operational: methods available, but each case needs to be prepared individually. Reference for the coastal hypoxia map for Finland: 10.5194/bg-16-3183-2019	Operational for one nation (Finland). Reference for the statistical species distribution modelling: 10.3389/fmars.2018.00402/full .	Operational for several routes crossing the Baltic Sea: https://www.finmari-infrastructure.fi/terrybox/

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